

21GRD08 SoMMet

D5: Report on the comparison of soil moisture measurement methods and their different sensing domains (local and remote) including details on the constraints and accuracy of the methods and requirements for harmonisation

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Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: UNIBO

Due date of the deliverable: September 2024

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30 November 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Deliverable **D5** of project 21GRD08 SoMMet

Report on the comparison of soil moisture measurement methods and their different sensing domains (local and remote) including details on the constraints and accuracy of the methods and requirements for harmonisation

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Glossary

SWC: Soil Water Content

PS: Point Scale

CRNS: Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing

RS: Remote Sensing

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Summary

This document, deliverable D5, is the fifth of eight technical deliverables of the project 21GRD08 SoMMet (hereafter: SoMMet). The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States (Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology; Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599; Grant number: 21GRD08 SoMMet).

This report summarizes the main results achieved during the SoMMet project within Task 3.1 of Work Package 3. The aim of this task was to characterize and extract information on soil water content (SWC) as determined by point-scale (PS), cosmic-ray neutron sensing (CRNS), and remote sensing (RS) methods. The main systematic effects affecting the SWC measurements and their associated uncertainties for each method were also discussed.

First, a systematic review of the methods used to characterize spatial and temporal soil moisture observations was conducted. It was found that SWC observations are typically well defined in terms of precision and accuracy: precision referring to the reproducibility of the observations, and accuracy referring to their deviation from a benchmark. While both concepts are universally accepted, the definition of a SWC benchmark varies depending on the study and the scientific community. In many cases, the loss-on-drying method is considered the standard. However, when comparing SWC observations obtained from different methods with different sensing characteristics, the number of samples, the sampling design, and the collection periods vary significantly.

Some improvements in the characterization of SWC observations have been introduced with the "triplet" concept (Western and Bloschl, 1999). Specifically, the authors proposed explicitly defining: (1) the extent, as the area under study; (2) the support, as the sensing volume; and (3) the spacing, as the distance between observation points. While other terms are also found in the literature (e.g., resolution, density), we found that integrating this concept can help reduce discrepancies in observation assessments reported in different studies. Notably, all three methods (PS, CRNS, and RS) ultimately have an arbitrary support, defined by assumptions that are only valid under certain conditions.

The review also identified the representativeness concept as a promising avenue for further work. This concept has long been recognized as relevant for defining any observation (Nappo et al., 1982), but various definitions exist based on different assumptions, and its practical application in the literature remains limited.

Based on this review, the research activities focused on analysing SWC time series collected by the different methods, specifically emphasizing the triplet concept and representativeness. Both historical time series and new dedicated experiments were used. Results have been presented and discussed at different international conferences and published. The present deliverable presents and discusses the main outcomes.

Overall, we found that explicitly considering the support and representativeness of observations helps explain differences between measurements that might otherwise be interpreted as errors. For instance, SWC time series were affected by differences in land use and management. In these cases, all observations were correct, and the discrepancies could be explained by differences in the

environmental factors influencing the measurements. For this reason, we argue that many studies performing direct intercomparisons of observations from different methods should be interpreted with caution. Instead, more rigorous analyses of the factors affecting the SWC dynamics detected by each specific method are needed.

While we conclude that the use of any representativeness index would be beneficial, within the SoMMet project we have started to develop a new pragmatic representativeness index. This index will be tested with additional datasets, and an additional manuscript is foreseen.

1 Review on the existing methods to characterize spatial and temporal soil moisture observations

A systematic review of the methods used to characterize spatial and temporal soil moisture observations was conducted and discussed during the SoMMet meetings.

The review started by acknowledging how accuracy and precision are terms well defined and accepted in all the studies and scientific communities. Precision can be defined as how close the measurements are to each other. In contrast, accuracy can be defined as how close a given set of measurements are to their “true value”. As example, these concepts are represented in Figure 1. Based on these, a number of statistical metrics have been defined, like correlation, bias, root square mean error (RMSE) or combinations of them (Gupta et al., 2009).

Figure 1. Examples of observations, from left: precise and accurate; accurate but not precise; precise but not accurate; not accurate and not precise (Figure source: Wikipedia).

Noteworthy, within the project is however argued that a “true value” cannot be defined. For this reason, the term “benchmark” has been preferred. Moreover, when looking at the soil water content (SWC) observations, the definition of a benchmark varies depending on the study and on the scientific community. For example, point-scale (PS) sensors are typically calibrated and validated in the laboratory under controlled conditions, where good assessments are usually achieved. In contrast, during field installations, practices vary from specific experience-based approaches to the use of standard calibration functions from the literature. CRNS is generally calibrated using approximately 100 soil samples collected within a single day over the sensing area. This approach assumes that CRNS adequately captures the temporal dynamics of SWC, and only the absolute values require scaling. RS SWC products, in contrast, are usually calibrated using a few locations where time series from PS sensors are available. This approach relies on the fact that PS observations are often sparse within RS pixel areas. Consequently, the definition of a benchmark remains questionable. Moreover, because RS dynamics may also require scaling, long time series are preferable for assessment. Based on this first overview, it was highlighted how different methods might have different expectation and benchmark. Thus, intercomparison between the method might not be straightforward.

The systematic review has also identified another interesting concept that has been further discussed. Specifically, in some studies (Western and Bloschl, 1999) it is suggested to explicitly define: (1) the extent, as the area under study; (2) the support, as the sensing volume; and (3) the spacing, as the distance between observation points (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Definition of the scale triplet (spacing, extent and support). Adopted after (Western and Bloschl, 1999).

While other terms are also found in literature (e.g., resolution, density), it has been acknowledged how this “triplet” concept can help reducing discrepancies in observation assessments reported in different studies. For instance, the support of the CRNS signal is a topic under continuous discussion. It has been arbitrarily defined as the area from where 86 % of signal is detected and it has initially assumed as a constant volume with radius of 200 m (Desilets and Zreda, 2013). Later (Schrön et al., 2017) it has been argued that the sensitivity from the sensor strongly decreases, the footprint is smaller than previously assumed (around 80 –120 m radius) and it changes in time as a function of the SWC (or hydrogen). This has provided more insight into the interpretation of the method but it also limited the applicability of this methodology and, to some degree, the acceptance by other scientific communities. In contrast, the support of PS and RS observations are generally considered constant and well defined. By searching for more dedicated studies on the topic, it has been found, however, that in both cases also their support should be considered with caution. When looking at PS sensors, it is noted how generally they measure an electric signal. For this reason their signal in the soil is also not uniform and it might change over time (Ferré et al., 1998). Due to the relatively small space differences, however, the sensors are considered as “point-scale” and the actual support is only considered when specific laboratory intercomparisons are performed. Finally, RS support is usually defined by the grid image resolution. Nowadays, for instance, high resolutions RS products are published at 1 km grid. However, this is often the effect of the resampling of different products that comes with different resolutions. For this reason the actual resolution based on the signal contribution might be different (Brocca et al., 2024). Similarly, penetration depth of the RS signal is often assumed to be around the first 5 cm of soil. However, it has also been argued that this penetration is not constant and could depend on the specific conditions (Feldman et al., 2023).

Overall, focusing on the triplet approach for the assessment of the SWC observations showed how all three methods (PS, CRNS, and RS) ultimately have an arbitrary support, defined by assumptions that are only valid under certain conditions. Thus, assessment, proper intercomparisons and data fusion should account for that.

In searching for a more coherent characterization of the observations, we finally focused on representativeness. This concept has long been recognized as relevant for defining any observation (Nappo et al., 1982). We found that the concept has been rigorously discussed from both statistical and practical point of view. Several indices have been then proposed. As examples, by looking specifically into SWC observations, it is worth citing the temporal stability concept (Vauchedet al., 1985), the inverse footprint (Orlowsky and Seneviratne 2014) and the triple collocation (see Gruber

et al., 2013). Despite this rich discussion, however, it has been found that the use of representativeness indices in literature is still very limited and most of the studies compare observations without accounting for that. Among others, some reasons might be related to the need of several observations to calculate the index that are not always available or strong assumptions in the applicability of the index that cannot be justified.

To overcome some of these limitations, we have started to develop a new representativeness index based on the fact that the degree of representativeness of a measurement is ultimately determined by the temporal and spatial variability of the quantity being measured. For this reason, factors that influence space-time variability also influence representativeness (Nappo et al., 1982). Specifically, by analysing the factors variability affecting SWC, i.e., weather, topography, vegetation and soil, we can infer representativeness of a SWC observation. We hypothesis that avoiding the need of additional SWC observations for quantifying representativeness will provide the possibility to apply this approach without limitations and will put the basis for a more rigours use, interpretation and comparison of observations.

2 Quantify and compare the information content, strength, and weakness of each soil moisture measurement method

We performed several intercomparisons between SWC observations obtained from point-scale (PS), cosmic-ray neutron-sensing (CRNS) and remote sensing (RS), specifically accounting for the concepts identified and discussed in the previous section (triplet and representativeness). First analyses have been conducted based on previously processed data (Gianessi et al., 2024). Additional analyses have been performed based on the new data collected within the SoMMet project at the high-level field sites. The analyses have been presented and discussed at several conferences (MMC2023, EGU2024). One paper has been published (Emamalizadeh et al., 2024) and one paper is currently under review (Mazzoleni et al., under review). In this section the main outcomes are briefly summarized. We refer to the published paper for more details (Emamalizadeh et al., 2024).

The SWC observations have been collected following the general experimental design shown in Figure 3 at two sites, as example. PS SWC observations have been collected at different locations during dedicated field surveys (yellow points in the figure 3). Time-series of PS SWC were available only in specific cases (high-level sites) and only in few locations. CRNS sensors were calibrated based on standard approaches (Zreda et al., 2012) and SWC time-series have been referred to the average support depicted in the figure 3 as green circle. RS SWC were downloaded based on available product at 1 km resolution and the standard square grid in yellow has been considered for the interpretation.

The assessment of the SWC observations has been integrated with the analysis of the factors affecting SWC dynamics, namely, topography, atmospheric conditions, vegetation, and soil properties (Crow et al., 2012). The areas investigated in these analyses were however relatively small and flat. For this reason, we assumed that topography and atmospheric variability is negligible within the studied areas. The assessment of the vegetation was based on the NDVI (Rouse et al., 1974), a widely used remote sensing vegetation index that can capture temporal and spatial variability of the plants and their vigour. Soil properties and soil variability was detected based on both global soil data base (Poggio et al., 2021) and dedicated soil texture analyses. Moreover, since the experimental sites belong to agricultural cropped fields, agricultural managements practices were recorded when possible (e.g., irrigation events).

Figure 3. Examples of experimental design with locations and spatial characteristics of the SWC observations: point TDR sampling refers to the PS SWC; red dot and green circle refer to the CRNS location and footprint; SWI pixel refers to the RS support (source (Emamalizadeh et al., 2024)).

Figure 4. Intercomparison between CRNS and RS SWC products at two locations. Average PS SWC values are depicted when available (TDR). Source (Emamalizadeh et al., 2024).

The results of the intercomparison obtained at two experimental sites are shown in Figure 4, as example. Good agreement between the SWC observations is generally observed, with dynamics

that well respond to precipitation events. Noteworthy, August onwards, divergence on the absolute values emerged with RS-derived SWC that tended to be higher than CRNS and PS values.

The results have been interpreted in the light of vegetation and soil differences. It was found that lower agreement between CRNS and RS was achieved when NDVI values is relatively high, confirming the possible contribution of the vegetation on the RS signal. Some relations have also been identified by looking at the soil properties. Specifically, the best agreement between the SWC products has been found at the site where we had the loam soil (with a high percentage of sand and SOC in comparison to other sites) and a relatively low spatial variability within the RS pixel. In contrast, the other sites where we obtained lower agreements between the SWC products have higher percentages of silt and clay and higher spatial variability.

Ultimately, the comparison focused on the periods where irrigations took place (Figure 5). The results showed some inconsistency between the SWC products on the irrigation events. CRNS responded well to the irrigation events. In contrast, RS signal did not see one event, and it increased earlier and to a lesser extent to the others.

While these results should suggest some uncertainties in the RS product, some more insights have been developed by considering irrigation management over the area. Specifically, it should be noted that not all the fields with the RS pixel are irrigated simultaneously smoothing or anticipating the effect of the irrigation of the CRNS area over the RS pixel.

Figure 5. Intercomparison between CRNS and RM SWC products at two locations with the focus on the dynamic during irrigation event. Source (Emamalzadeh et al., 2024).

3 Conclusion

The research activities conducted within this task ranges from a systematic review of literatures to several comprehensive comparisons between SWC observations obtained by PS, CRNS and RS methods. Based on that, several contributions have been presented and discussed at different international conferences. Some papers have been published, one paper is under review and one paper is in preparation.

Overall, the results identified the triplet (extent, support and spacing) and the representativeness as relevant concepts that should be considered for the characterization and intercomparison of the observations. More specifically, the results obtained during the project showed how vegetation, soil and land management could be relevant factors in explaining the different agreements in the SWC products. Thus, the application of these concepts a better perspective in the interpretation of the differences between the methods disentangling the errors from the inherent nature of the specific detected signal.

Based on these results, it is recommended to assess the influence of the environmental factors affecting the specific observation to better support intercomparisons and data fusion approaches. Alternatively, this analysis could help identifying the location of the observations to be more informative. While at present, the use of any representativeness index would be beneficial, it is also acknowledged that within the SoMMet project we have started to develop a new pragmatic representativeness index that is now under testing based on new data sets.

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